

DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3835917>

Leiodinychus orbicularis (C.L. Koch, 1839) in bat boxes in Poland

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Received: 25 March 2020; Revised submission: 27 April 2020; Accepted: 19 May 2020

<http://www.journals.tmkarpinski.com/index.php/ejbr>

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ABSTRACT: The presented studies are the first one on the occurrence of mites in bat boxes and focuses on Uropodina (Acari: Mesostigmata). Investigation was carried out in Western Poland in October 2015. Guano was collected from 58 bat boxes occupied by 10 species of bats. Excrements from particular bat boxes were placed separately in string bags and transported to the laboratory. The extracted fauna was preserved in 75% ethanol and mites were identified with stereoscopic light microscope. The study revealed only one species of Uropodina mite on bat guano in the studied bat boxes, namely *Leiodinychus orbicularis* (C.L. Koch, 1839).

Keywords: Bats; Guano; *Leiodinychus orbicularis*; Nidicolous species.

1. INTRODUCTION

Previous studies shown, that bat guano in caves, constitute a habitat for mites belonging to suborder Uropodina. These mites create communities consisting of species that usually occur in unstable habitats [1]. In European caves, two Uropodina species were recorded on the guano, namely: *Phaulodiaspis rackei* (Oudemans, 1912) and *Phaulodiaspis advena* (Trägårdh, 1912) [2-4]. In this study we aimed to check if guano in bat boxes is also inhabited by mites from suborder Uropodina. The investigation presented here is a first on the subject.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The guano was collected in October 2015 from 58 bat boxes occupied by 10 species of bats, namely *Eptesicus serotinus* (Schreber, 1774), *Myotis brandtii* (Eversmann, 1845), *Myotis myotis* (Borkhausen, 1797), *Myotis mystacinus* (Kuhl, 1817), *Myotis nattereri* (Kuhl, 1817), *Nyctalus leisleri* (Kuhl, 1817), *Nyctalus noctula* (Schreber, 1774), *Pipistrellus nathusii* (Keyserling and Bläsius, 1839), *Pipistrellus pygmaeus* (Leach, 1825), *Plecotus auritus* (Linnaeus, 1758) [5-7]. The occurrence of Uropodina mites however, was not considered in relation to particular species of bats, since in a one bat box the guano might have been produced

protonymphs: 41; larva: 1). All individuals belonged to one species, namely *Leiodinychus orbicularis* (C.L. Koch, 1839).

Leiodinychus orbicularis (Figure 2) is known from Europe as well as Algeria and India [3, 11-15]. It is coprophilous and saprophagous, and occurs in various decaying substrates such as compost or manure [3]. This mite is also a frequent inhabitant of nests and nestboxes [3, 16-25] and thus may be considered as nidicolous species [1, 3, 13] (Table 1). *Leiodinychus orbicularis* rarely occurs also in other type of habitats such as xerophilous grasses, meadows, alder forests, hornbeam forests, mixed deciduous forests, beech-wood on lowland, oak-woods, yew-tree stands, mixed forests (with pine), parks, nest of small mammals, rotten trunks and hollows in trees [16 and unpublished data]. Our study shows that *L. orbicularis* also occurs in bat boxes and dwells in guano of these mammals.

Figure 2. *Leiodinychus orbicularis* - female, dorsal side (A) and ventral side (B); male - ventral side (C).

In this study we did not discover European Uropodina mites that have been already recorded on bats guano in caves, i.e. *Phaulodinychus rackei* (Oudemans, 1912) and *Pahulodinychus advena* (Trägårdh, 1912) [2, 9, 10, 26]. The absence of *P. advena* in bat boxes in Western Poland may result from the geographical range of this species; it occurs in Czech Republic, Slovakia, France, Germany, Austria, Hungary and Romania [3] while in Poland it reaches its northern border of the range and occurs only in southern part of the country [16] (Figure 1). On the other hand, *P. rackei* previously classified as coprophilous that dwells on bat guano [2], seem to be associated mostly with nests of moles in Central Europe [1, 3, 16].

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, *L. orbicularis* is attracted to the guano of both bats in bat boxes and birds in nestboxes conversely to other species from this group of mites which have different trophic requirements. On the other hand, the species was not recorded in bat guano in caves probably due to its preferences to warmer and drier environments than caves. Presence of only one representative of Uropodina mites on guano in bat boxes may be also related with specific entomofauna inhabiting bat boxes since these mites use phoresy for spreading between the unstable microhabitats and show high selectivity for a species of a carrier [3, 4].

Table 1. Habitat preferences of *L. orbicularis* in Poland: N – number of samples; F – frequency (%); Ns – number of positive samples; X – mean of specimens/per positive sample, Nsp – number of specimens.

Habitat	N	F	Ns	X±SD	Nsp
Open habitat					
Xerophilous grasses	97	1.03	1	8	8
Sandhills	27	-	-	-	-
Rocks grasses (noncalcareous)	159	-	-	-	-
Rocks grasses on limestone	105	-	-	-	-
Meadows	1,192	2.52	30	45.13±130.64	1,354
Moorlands	18	-	-	-	-
Peat-bogs	87	-	-	-	-
Sedgeland	415	-	-	-	-
Agrocenoses	8	-	-	-	-
<i>Schoenoplectus</i> and reed beds	5	-	-	-	-
Forest and shrubs					
Alder forest – soil and litter	212	0.47	1	2	2
Marshy forest – soil and litter	621	-	-	-	-
Hornbeam forest – soil and litter	7,100	0.13	9	6.15±13.06	80
Mixed deciduous forest – soil and litter	735	0.14	1	1	1
Beech-wood on lowland – soil and litter	158	0.63	1	1	1
Beech-wood in the mountain – soil and litter	864	-	-	-	-
Oak-wood – only soil and litter	75	1.33	1	1	1
Pine forest – only soil and litter	1,508	-	-	-	-
Spruce forest in the mountain – soil and litter	509	-	-	-	-
Spruce forest on lowland – soil and litter	82	-	-	-	-
Fir forest – soil and litter	234	-	-	-	-
Larch stand – soil and litter	46	-	-	-	-
Yew-tree stand – soil and litter	244	0.82	2	4±4.24	8
Fir-beech forest – soil and litter	86	-	-	-	-
Mixed forest (with pine) – soil and litter	730	2.60	19	23.31±52.27	433
Mixed forest (with spruce) – soil and litter	105	-	-	-	-
Dwarf pine	60	-	-	-	-
Brushwood	358	-	-	-	-
Parks – soil and litter	410	2.20	9	7.56±8.38	68
Merocenoses					
Ant-hills	42	-	-	-	-
Nest of small mammals	242	0.83	2	3.5±8.38	7
Nest of birds	823	10.94	90	31.54±93.78	2,839
Rot trunks	1,376	0.80	11	2.00±3.54	32
Hollows in tree	244	4.10	10	9.10±13.50	51
Bark of tree	87	-	-	-	-
Total	18,160	2.06	187		4,885

Authors' Contributions: JB: Identification of the species; Conception of the paper and design of the first version of the manuscript; Analysis and interpretation of data. TR: Collection of material; Segregation of material in samples; Technical support. GW: Organization of field research; Material collection. ZKP:

Conception of the paper; Interpretation of data; Translation into English. MZ: Segregation of material in samples; Analysis of environmental data; AN: Conception of the paper; Preparation of the final version of the manuscript; Linguistic correction.

Conflict of Interest: The authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

Acknowledgements: Authors are grateful to Paweł Kmiecik, Grzegorz Lesiński, Maurycy Ignaczak, Wojciech Stephan and Jarosław Manias who helped with material collection.

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